

WATER AND WATER USE ISSUES, AS WELL AS ENTERPRISE WATER SUPPLY SYSTEMS

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Annotation. *This article addresses the challenges associated with assessing water usage in industrial enterprises, particularly in the context of towel production. It discusses both industrial water consumption and household water usage in production processes, as well as irrigation needs and regulatory standards. Additionally, it examines the chemical composition of water from artesian wells, which serve as a primary water source for the organization.*

Keywords: *Artesian water consumption, calculations, error propagation, pollutants, analysis, contingency planning, industrial zone, parameters.*

Introduction

The sluggish implementation of various decisions and decrees by our country has resulted in inadequate supply by both the population and enterprise organizations, leading to ecological disturbances and water body pollution. Cabinet of Ministers Decree No. 401, dated October 4, 2001, titled "On Measures to Improve the Environmental and Sanitary Epidemiological Situation in the Water Bodies of the Zarafshan River Region," along with Decree No. 174, dated April 7, 2000, about focusing on the protection of underground and open water sources and spring water, mandates the monitoring of water protection zones regulated under the directive, specifically for water sources utilized in treatment and cultural-healthcare facilities.

Methods. To ensure sanitary-epidemiological reliability at water intake facilities, designated sanitary protection zones and regions are established around water supply sources within water intake areas. These requirements are mandatory for all water consumers, prohibiting economic activities and the use of any means against plant pests, diseases, or weeds. Notably, water consumption for daily life in urban areas is notably high in developed capitalist countries worldwide.

Industrial water usage is determined by the volume and type of products manufactured. Norms for water consumption are established based on enterprise characteristics, either for the main production line or specific product types. The water consumption norm serves as a tool to evaluate the efficiency of water usage in each operating enterprise.

Analysis and Results. The construction of a soft feather towel production facility at QUASAR LLC, located in Jizzakh, Uzbekistan, has yielded the following outcomes.

Fabric Preparation. The manufacturing process involves aerating natural cotton blended with hemp and bamboo. Cotton, known for its softness and water

absorption properties, is enhanced by longer starting fibers, resulting in stronger and more absorbent material. The base of the soft fabric comprises thin threads. Bamboo can also be incorporated to produce soft feather towel material, characterized by its shine and smoothness. Material preparation may involve single-type or mixed homogenous materials, such as cotton and bamboo or hemp and bamboo.

Towel Manufacturing. Towels are crafted using small to medium fibers, ensuring durability and color retention for up to 500 washes. However, the preparation process of soft feather gauze using SC-2200x1000/N-7-672 and QTECH-3600x1250/N-7-672 machines releases inorganic dust into the atmosphere.

Machine Specifications. The SC-2200X1000/N-7-672 and QTECH-3600x1250/N-7-672 machines, along with the splittail WTECH-SS-3600X1250 machine, operate at a speed of 1000 m/min, with a pressure of 6 Bars and a power consumption of 21 kW. The valve diameter measures 1000 mm. These machines are products of "KUCUKER MAKINA SANAYII VE TICARET A.S.," originating from Turkey.

Material Tightness Control. The high-speed-Q-ART SERIES equipment, equipped with a Weighing & Barcode Printer System, imported from Turkey, ensures the quality and tightness control of the material.

Painting Process: The painting section includes the installation of painting and compression equipment (1 set), two pieces of drying and ironing equipment, a small boiler, and two laboratory measuring instruments.

Dyeing Process and Environmental Regulations: In compliance with the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan's registration on January 3, 2006, No. 1533, "Instructions for Accounting for Sources Emitting Pollutants into the Atmosphere and Normalizing Pollutants in Enterprises in the Territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan," Annex 1.7, band 1.7.2 outlines the emission of butylacetate, hydrocarbons, toluene, and ethylbenzene into the atmosphere during the dyeing process.

Use of Heat-Resistant Fapromxide Powder: Heat-resistant Fapromxide powder, with 99.47% solid particle content and 0.53% volatile compounds, is extracted during the dyeing process.

Gas Consumption and Environmental Impact: A small boiler is utilized for drying painted materials in Tsex, with an annual natural gas consumption of 79,200 m³. According to Application 1.13 of the "Directive for Accounting for Sources of Pollutants in the Atmosphere and Normalization of Pollutants in Enterprises in the Territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan," registered with the Ministry of Justice on January 3, 2006, combustion of natural gas emits carbon monoxide and nitrous oxide into the atmosphere.

Pollutant Release during Heating Processes: Pollutants released into the atmosphere during heating processes follow specific technological procedures.

$$M_{\text{NO}_2} = 0,001 * B * Q_{\text{H}} * K_{\text{NO}_2} * (1-v)$$

Where: Q_{H} is the heat of the fuel in combustion, mDj per kg or mDj per cubic meter.

The parameter K_{NO_2} - 1 Gdj represents the creation of nitric oxide during heat generation ($K_{\text{NO}_2} = 0.005$), while the technical coefficient v accounts for the degree of pollution reduction.

$$M_{\text{CO}} = 0,001 * B * C_{\text{CO}} * (1 - q_4/100), \text{ here}$$

C_{CO} - SSO-liquid (t/yr, (g/sec) or gaseous in the state, (thousand m³/yr) the emission of carbon monoxide (is gas) when the fuel burns, g/m³, is determined by the following formula:

$$C_{\text{CO}} = q_3 * R * Q_{\text{H}},$$

Q_3, q_4 – coefficient that takes into account the loss of heat from mechanical and chemical non-combustion of fuel;

V - fuel consumption, g / sek, t / Year;

Q_{H} is the heat of the fuel in combustion, mDj/kg or mDj/m³ 1 kal = 4.1868 Dj).

Q_3, Q_4 coefficients are assumed to be equal to 0.5 in the absence of exploitative data. When using gas as fuel, the formula will look like this:

$$M_{\text{CO}} = 0,001 * B * 0,5 * 0,5 * Q_{\text{H}} * 0,995$$

Material Cutting Section: The material cutting section is equipped with the High Speed AZIMO 222 FULL AUTOMATIC LONGITUDINAL HEMMING and STITCHING machine, as well as the AZIMO 333 FULL AUTOMATIC LONGITUDINAL CUTTING upright and bed tearing machine. Technical specifications for these machines include: 380 V AC, 50 Hz, 5/6 kW, with dimensions of 4500 mm (width), 5000 mm (length), and 3100 mm (height). The diameter is 2000 mm. These machines are manufactured by Azim Tekstil San.ve Tic Paz. A.S., Turkey. Inorganic dust is released into the atmosphere during these processes.

Border Giving Section: This section is equipped with a multi-head automatic rimming unit TFSN-915 (680x400) S and a one-head automatic rimming unit TMBP-S1201C (360x500) S, imported from the Japanese firm Tajima Industries Ltd.

Sewing Section: The sewing section features a BML-9300-D4 machine from the Chinese state firm Baoyu, capable of performing computerized tasks automatically, along with averlock BML-6800-D4 machines for high-altitude, energetic work. Technical specifications for these machines include: power of 550 W, 220 V AC, 50 Hz, and a speed of 5500 stitches per minute. Inorganic dust is released into the atmosphere as a result of operating these machines.

Water Consumption: Water for the enterprise is sourced from an artesian well

under the account of "Jizzakh Plastic" Join-stock company . According to technological regulations, 50% water is used per product per 1 kg of paintbrush powder. With an annual production capacity of 1800 tons/year of towels of different colors and an annual consumption of 150 tons of paint powder, the water consumption for production is calculated as follows:

$$Q = M \cdot 12 \cdot 50\% = 150 \cdot 12 \cdot 50\% = 900 \text{ m}^3/\text{year},$$

0,9 thousand m³/year or 3,1 m³/per day

The water consumption for the communication network is determined based on the water consumption required for the installed devices, as per directive QMQ 2.04.01-98 "Internal Water Supply."

Equipment name	Number	Water consumption in 1 hour, л	Total, l/h
Lavatory	4	30	120
Toilet	2	100	200
Total	6		320

The total one-hour usage is 0.32 m³. The supply of sanitary equipment is used for approximately one hour every day. So, the daily water use is 0.32 m³/day, while the annual consumption is 92.8 m³/year, or 0.0928 thousand m³/year. The approximate water usage for household and household demands is estimated using QMQ 2.04.01-97. Each worker consumes 25 liters of water per milk. 25 * 250 workers equals 6250 l/milk, or 6.25 m³/milk. A year consists of 290 working days. To calculate annual water consumption, multiply 290 by 6250, which is 1812500 l/year or 1812.5 m³/year (1.8125 thousand m³/year).

Water consumption in the kitchen. $W(\text{day/night}) = N \cdot R / 1000$ Here: n-1 serving is the norm of water needed for cooking ($N = 25 \text{ dm}^3/\text{meal}$); R-number of seats in the kitchen (60 people); T-number of working days in a year (290 days). $W(\text{day-night}) = 25 \cdot 60 / 1000 = 1.5 \text{ m}^3$ per milk. $W(\text{year}) = W(\text{day/night})$

$T^*/1000 = 1.5 \cdot 290 / 1000 = 0.435$ thousand m³ per year. To calculate the quantity of water wasted on the dishwasher bath, use the formula:

$$W(\text{day-night}) = N \cdot r \cdot t / 1000$$

Here: N is the norm of water spent on the washing bath, $N = 200 \text{ m}^3/\text{hour}$; R is the number of baths, 2 PCs; t is the working duration of the bath in one day, 2 hours;

T is the number of working days in a year, $T = 290$. $W(\text{day-night}) = 200 \cdot 2 \cdot 2 / 1000 = 0.8 \text{ m}^3$ per milk.

$$W(\text{year}) = W(\text{day-night}) T^* / 1000 = 0.8.$$

Water spent on firefighting

A 20 m³ water pond is located on the facility's grounds and serves as a fire water

reserve.

The amount of water spent on the pond equals 10% of its volume. Water consumption is calculated as: $Q=20*10\%=2.0\text{m}^3/\text{milk}$. $II = 2.0 \times 365/1000 = 0.73 \text{ min m}^3/\text{year}$.

Waste water accounting

Effluents produced during agricultural drinking activities Effluent from agricultural drinking activities accounts for 30% of the water used for employee drinking. The wastewater produced is comparable to: 1,875 m³ per day. and 0.5437,000 m³ annually.

Effluents generated during culinary activities. In the kitchen, wastewater accounts for 40% of the water consumed during cooking and 100% when washing dishes. The wastewater produced is comparable to 1.4 m³ per milk and 0.406,000 m³ annually. Effluents generated by the network of communications. Effluent from the communications network accounts for 100% of the water used.

The wastewater produced is comparable to 0.32 m³/night and 0.0928 thousand m³/year. The water requirements of the firm are shown in the table below.

Consumer name	The amount of water consumed per day (m³ / per day)	Annual amount of Water spent (thousand m³/year)
Farm-drink	6,25	1,8125
Farm-Household	0,32	0,0928
For producing	3,1	0,900
For kitchen	2,3	0,667
Fire Reserve	2,0	0,73
Total water usage	13,97	4,2023
Total wastewater usage	3,595	1,0425

Conclusion. The wastewater generated at the facility is sent to the Jizzakh plastic Joint-stock Company enterprise sewer network and then to the Jizzakh city sewer network. The volume of wastewater produced is 3,595 m³/day (1,0425,000 m³/year). Rainwater is routed by concrete ditches to local ditch networks.

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